

TYPICAL TRANSLATION ERRORS IN TRANSMISSION OF NON-EQUIVALENT VOCABULARY

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Annotation: In this article discussed about typical translation errors in transmission of non-equivalent vocabulary

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The study of translation arose as a new academic area throughout the twentieth century, with a concentration on the last thirty years in particular . During the time, translation was mostly concentrated on literary works. Poets from all over the world attempted to publicize their works so that everyone would be aware of them. The issue was that not everyone understood the languages.

Through the history, written and spoken translations also interpreting have played a vital role in inter-human communication, for example in providing contact to important texts for scholarship and religious purposes. Yet the study of translation as an academic subject has only really begun in the past sixty years. In the English speaking countries, this discipline is now normally known as translation studies .

Translation is an important thing to learn in our world. It is necessary not just for education. Since technology is so common, translation has become important in almost every part of people's lives. Translation means changing something from one form to another. Form refers to the way we use language, like the words, phrases, and sentences we use to speak or write.

The term translation itself is described as a process of changing an original text in the original language into a different language by the translator . Translation means taking a message or meaning from one language and putting it into another language. Translation is not just changing words from one language to another but also making sure the message is understood correctly. So, it's important to translate it accurately from the original language to the new language. If we understand each other properly, we won't have any confusion or mistakes.

There are some criteria to determine whether the translation is good or not, they are use the normal language forms of the receptor language, communicates as much as possible to the receptor language speakers the same meaning that was understood by the speakers of the source language, and maintains the dynamics of the original source language text .

Translation is not an easy work to be done as it is not simply the substitution of words in one language by another language, but the transmission of meaning and sense that the translator wants to convey in the most natural way. Therefore, it requires the training of prospective translators which are done carefully in order to produce efficient translators (Cúc, 2018).

Based on these criteria, it can be deduced that translating involves at least two factors: the sender or the source language to be translated and the receiver or the target language into which translators must translate . Translators must overcome any issues that arise during the translation process since translation entails combining two cultures, two perspectives, two

languages, and other factors into a single solid written content that the recipient will understand.

Translators require what is known as translational competence, which Pym defines as :

- The ability to generate a TT(target text) series of more than one viable term (TT1, TT2...TTn) for a ST(source text).
- The ability to select only one TT from this series, quickly and with justified confidence, and to propose this TT as a replacement of ST for a specified purpose and reader.

To the extent as their union concerns translation and nothing else, these two talents comprise a distinctively translational ability. They have little to do with language proficiency. There is no question that translators must be well-versed in grammar, rhetoric, terminology, global knowledge, common sense, and payment tactics, yet the translational aspect of their work is strictly neither linguistic, common, nor commercial . It is a process of creating and comparing alternative texts. The writer believes that the title here is relevant to discuss because most translators encounter problems throughout the translation process. Not only can amateur translators make mistakes while starting a translation, but expert translators do as well. How do these faults occur, and how do they be corrected? The chapter describes these faults in this dissertation work.

Errors in translation mostly result from the non-equivalence between the source and target languages . However, good translators with encyclopedic knowledge and linguistic knowledge of both the source and target languages know how to deal with them; therefore, errors can indicate the quality of a translation; moreover, they can reveal what is going on in the translator's thinking process .

In a language contact situation, Wilss defines a translation mistake as an offence against a norm. We may conclude from these definitions of translation faults that there are many components to translating, not only how to translate the text meaningfully, but also translators must pay attention to the context connected to the culture and conditions under which the text can be used. That is not an easy assignment for translators. If the expression or text is difficult to grasp, even for translators, the role of translation is not fulfilled. Translation errors are frequently linked to one another. It signifies that one error or difficulty has an effect on other errors. The answer follows suit. Because the faults are linked, the answers for one problem will impact the solutions for others . It is as though there are networks or hierarchies in which the answer to one problem effects how other problems are addressed. If a translation error is defined as a failure to carry out the instructions implied in the translation brief and as inadequate solutions to a translation problem, then translation errors can be classified into four categories :

1. Pragmatic translation errors caused by inadequate solutions to pragmatic translation problems such as a lack of receiver orientations.

The fundamental issue with pragmatic translation mistakes is that the recipients are often unaware that they are receiving incorrect information . This is one of the most essential decisions a translator may make. This is due to the fact that the initial decision in the translation process refers to the translation type that is most suited to the translation purpose, and each subsequent step is directed by this decision. When translators commit these pragmatic mistakes, the entire translation process fails. They can only overcome these flaws by having someone with translational expertise compare the source and target texts in

light of the translation brief. For instance, certain phrases or sentences in our national works generate a pragmatic condition in the text that is exclusive to our country. It is important to be a representative of the Uzbek country in order to comprehend these nuances. For example, “Borakallo!” is the single word. As demonstrated by our example, even if the creator does not include any information about who spoke the term, his gender, or age, the reader will quickly realize that the author of the line is an older guy . It is the translator’s true talent to portray the identical circumstance to a foreign reader.

***“Barakallo, bu yerdagi ishlardan aql
hurkadi!”***

***“Well, well! Local affairs can come in horror”
Or consider another example:***

***“-Faqirning ostonasini ne maqsad bilan
so'radi kimyogar.”***

In this example, there is the word “faqir”, which does not mean poor, but the first person pronoun (I), which reflects Uzbek humility . The translator must convey this situation to the reader in the following sense:

-Why have you come to my place? – he asked slowly but with an unsatisfied tone.

In addition to the foregoing, there are synonyms, phraseological combinations, and proverbs in the work that enrich his style, and finding an equivalent to them demonstrates how extensive the translator's vocabulary should be. It should be emphasized, however, that in certain circumstances, the translators use lexical repetition rather than synonymous techniques. As previously stated, pragmatics is the subjective attitude of language means towards the system of speech acts. Because of the variety of settings and functions, the pragmatic characteristics of language units might vary. When we examine invitation speech formulae, we may identify several:

I'd like to invite you to my home – Men Sizni uyimga taklif qilmoqchi edim.

Come and see me – Biznikiga kirib keting.

Come around – Kirib turing.

Drop round – Kirib turing.

Though all these expressions denote same meaning – invitation to one’s home, their pragmatic meanings are different. The expression “I’d like to invite you to my home” is rather formal, used in order to invite respected guests or foreign partners. “Come and see me” can be said to a relative, neighbor or acquainted person. The last two phrases are informal and are used for close friends or members of family. So, pragmatics is not less important in maintaining international dialogues. The use of parallels or metaphors plays an important role in articulating pragmatic meaning. They are very common in oral communication. Such comparative expressions as “as clear as a day”, “as busy as a bee”, “as brave as a lion”, etc. are very often heard in conversations. In order to render their meaning a translator should not translate them word-for-word but to find their proper equivalents. Some of them have direct or full equivalents:

as cunning as a fox – tulkidek ayor

as clear as a day – kundek ravshan.

The spread of national cultural boundaries through translation has a significant beneficial and enriching impact on the language. It is true that many new ideas, discoveries, conceptions, and

so on enter the language along with the translation, resulting in the creation of new linguistic components and figurative meanings. This is especially true when translating from a less established literary language. The literary language strengthens this nation's metaphorical potential, national culture, and spiritual growth. The creative start of translation is the foundation of a creative attitude towards native language, the source of trust in its potential and beauty. Geographical traits differ from other cultural concepts in that they are typically value-free, both politically and financially. Yet, their spread is determined by the prominence of their founding nation as well as their degree of distinctiveness.

U tusatdan bir guruh chilim chekib turgan yigitlarga ko'zi tushdiyu, ko'rmaslikka oldi.

Suddenly she saw some young men smoking chilim, tried pretending not to see.

(Chilim An oriental tobacco pipe with a long, flexible tube that draws the smoke through water contained in a bowl.)

While translating from Uzbek to English, translators may encounter certain issues in rendering words that imply something in Uzbek but have no meaning in English. So, how do we deal with this issue? It is a difficult assignment that must be completed. Before translating, it is vital to understand the cultures of both ethnicities. Translators can convey words more efficiently if they are familiar with the nationality and culture.

- Sovchi degan gap qayoqdan chiqqan? - Guli jahl bilan qo'l siltadi. - Hali unisi keladi qiyshayib, hali bunisi keladi, tugunini osiltirib! (Utkir Hoshimov. Dunyoning ishlari, 2015. -P.50)

-Why do we need sovchi? -Guli shook her hands with nervous. I don't need them. But, they are coming, coming, coming without getting permission.

(Sovchi-it may be he or she, who can go to someone's house to ask their daughter for a bride. Usually, uncles, aunts, or one of the relatives are asked to visit there in order to ask agreement for getting married.)

Lexicon plays an important part in the expression of national identity. This lexicon becomes a subject of research in linguistics since its semantization demands entering the cultural and historical context and becoming acquainted with the environment (natural and material). It is critical to distinguish between non-equivalent vocabulary and vocabulary that, while conceptually similar to another language, differs in terms of prototypes and some kind of errors above mentioned that come from non-equivalent vocabulary should be taken into consideration while translating any text or source.

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